

The Influence of Problem-Based Learning Model on Junior High School Students' Mathematical Communication Skills and Mathematical Beliefs

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ARTICLE INFO	ABSTRACT
Published Online: 21 August 2025	The purpose of this study is to examine the effect of the Problem-Based Learning (PBL) model implemented in the experimental class and to compare it with the scientific approach commonly applied in schools. This research is a quasi-experimental study with a posttest-only control group design. The population consisted of all seventh-grade students at SMP Diponegoro Depok, comprising six classes. The research sample was selected using the cluster random sampling technique, resulting in two classes: class VII.A as the experimental class applying the Problem-Based Learning model, and class VII.B as the control class applying the scientific approach. The instruments used consisted of test and non-test instruments, including a mathematical communication skills test and a mathematics belief questionnaire, both of which had passed content validity. The data analysis to examine the effect of the Problem-Based Learning model and the scientific approach employed Hotelling's T^2 test and the Independent Samples T-Test. The results showed that the Problem-Based Learning (PBL) model had a significant effect on students' mathematical communication skills and mathematics beliefs. Furthermore, PBL was superior to the scientific approach in terms of seventh-grade students' mathematical communication skills and mathematics beliefs in the topic of statistics.
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I. INTRODUCTION

Education is a deliberate and structured effort to shape individuals who possess humanistic qualities. Trianto (2018:5) states that ideal education is not merely aimed at directing students toward a specific profession, but also at equipping them with the ability to address various problems in daily life.

Twenty-first century skills are essential for individuals to compete in the global arena. This is reinforced by Taar & Palojoki (2022), who assert that education plays a vital role in helping students adapt and thrive in today's world. Therefore, education is expected to serve as a means of equipping students with the competencies required in the 21st century.

One of the 21st-century literacies that needs to be improved is mathematical communication skills. Mathematical communication skills are highly important in the field of mathematics, encompassing the ability to convey mathematical thoughts or ideas both orally and in writing, as

well as serving as a thinking tool that helps students develop patterns, solve problems, and draw conclusions. NCTM (2000) explains that mathematical communication refers to students' ability to convey concepts, formulas, or problemsolving strategies they have acquired, expressed through dialogues or interactions that occur within the classroom environment. As stated by Maya & Setiawan (2018), students' communication skills are a fundamental ability that must be possessed in learning mathematics; therefore, fostering mathematical communication skills is particularly appropriate for junior high school students. In reality, however, many students still have low mathematical communication skills. This aligns with the research conducted by Nugroho, Sutopo, & Pramesti (2018: 146), which states that the learning process tends to be oneway, where the teacher becomes the center of learning, delivering the material while students merely copy what is presented. When students are asked to raise questions, they tend to remain silent. This indicates that students' mathematical communication skills are still low. Most students remain silent when asked to give

questions, often chat with their peers while the teacher is explaining, and are reluctant to take notes on the teacher's explanations. In mathematics learning, the affective aspect also plays an important role. One crucial affective aspect is students' belief in mathematics. According to Kloosterman et al. (1996), such belief is a fundamental view that influences students' decisions or actions. Imran et al. (2017) indicate that the factors influencing students' mathematical beliefs include perceiving mathematics as a difficult, boring, and less engaging subject. The findings of Muhtarom et al. (2018) also state that students' beliefs about mathematics greatly determine how successful they are in learning the subject. The importance of mathematical belief lies in its role as a guide for students' attitudes and actions in the learning process. Students' beliefs about mathematics influence how they respond to their mathematics lessons (Widjajanti, 2009). Misconceptions, such as viewing mathematics as a difficult, highly abstract subject filled with formulas and only mastered by gifted children, cause many students to experience excessive anxiety when facing mathematics lessons or tests. Excessive anxiety, in turn, will negatively affect both the learning process and the outcomes achieved. The study by Isharyadi & Deswita (2017) found that 90% of students considered mathematics as a subject focused on memorizing formulas, 78% agreed or strongly agreed that solving mathematical problems is simply a matter of following the teacher's method, and 81% believed that each mathematical problem has only one correct answer. Imran et al. (2017) point out that factors influencing students' mathematical beliefs include their perception of mathematics as a difficult, boring, and uninteresting subject. Similarly, the research conducted by Muhtarom et al. (2018) affirms that students' beliefs about mathematics largely determine their success in learning it.

In general, Problem-Based Learning (PBL) is an instructional approach that places students at the center of the learning process. Students work together in small groups to explore and discuss uncertainties related to the lesson. The PBL model engages individuals in groups to use their intellect in identifying important, relevant problems that align with current situations (Rusman, 2017). Problem-Based Learning helps students make better connections between what they have learned and real-world problems. Arends & Kilcher (2010) state that Problem-Based Learning (PBL) is one of the student-centered learning models in which learners are encouraged to solve complex, ill-structured real-world problems. In general, schools or educational institutions are shifting from traditional teacher-dominated instruction toward more student-focused learning. Research by Chan et al. (2024) indicates that when the PBL method is introduced in contexts outside the Western world, substantial changes in the schools or institutions are necessary to ensure students can fully engage in PBL, while still respecting cultural differences and student interests.

Although many studies have been conducted, few have specifically examined the implementation of the ProblemBased Learning (PBL) model in developing students' mathematical communication skills and mathematical beliefs, particularly in statistics. In fact, based on preliminary field observations, many students still struggle to solve mathematical problems, regardless of whether they possess high, moderate, or low levels of mathematical belief. This study aims to empirically examine the effect of the Problem-Based Learning (PBL) model applied in the experimental class and to compare it with the scientific approach commonly used in schools. In addition to assessing the extent of the PBL model's influence, this study also aims to explore differences in the effects between the two instructional approaches on student learning outcomes, particularly in terms of mathematical communication skills and mathematical beliefs.

II. RESEARCH METHOD

The research employed a posttest-only control group design involving two classes, namely the experimental class and the control class. The experimental class was taught using the Problem Based Learning (PBL) model, while the control class used the scientific approach. After the implementation of each instructional method, a posttest was administered to assess the extent to which the PBL model and the scientific approach influenced the improvement of students' learning outcomes. A research instrument is a tool used to collect data in a study (Lestari & Mokhammad, 2015:163). The instruments used in this research consisted of tests and non-test instruments. The test was used to measure mathematical communication skills, while the non-test instrument was used to measure students' mathematical beliefs.

The population in this research included all seventh-grade students at SMP Diponegoro Depok, consisting of six classes. Out of the six available classes, two classes were selected as the research sample. The sample selection was conducted using cluster random sampling. The researcher randomly selected from the larger population so that the sample was determined based on class groups. The cluster random sampling method was also used to ensure the availability of the sample throughout the treatment period. Based on information from the mathematics teacher at SMP Diponegoro Depok, all classes had the same level of homogeneity, and there were no special or advanced classes, so high-achieving students were evenly distributed across all classes. The first class, VII-A, consisting of 30 students, received instruction using the cooperative learning model of the Problem Based Learning (PBL) type. The second class, VII-B, also with 30 students, was taught using the scientific approach.

The data analysis techniques used in this research were descriptive and inferential statistical techniques. Descriptive statistical techniques were used to describe the data, including minimum score, maximum score, mean, and standard

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deviation. Inferential statistical techniques were used to test the research hypotheses, in which the inferential techniques applied were Hotelling's T^2 test and the independent sample t-test.

III. RESULT & DISCUSSION

The research conducted at SMP Diponegoro Depok aims to determine the effect of the Problem-Based Learning (PBL) model on students' mathematical communication skills and mathematical beliefs. The research sample consisted of two classes: Class VII-A, taught using the Problem-Based Learning (PBL) model with 30 students, and Class VII-B, taught using the scientific approach with 30 students. The subject matter in this study was statistics.

Class VII-A served as the experimental class, applying the Problem-Based Learning (PBL) model, while Class VII-B was the control class, applying the scientific learning approach. Each class had a total of four sessions: three sessions for the implementation of the treatment and one session for the post-test and the administration of the mathematical belief questionnaire.

In this study, the data analyzed were the post-test scores obtained from both classes. After the data were tabulated, the following data description was obtained.

Table 1. Students' Mathematical Communication Skills Data

Class	Number of Students	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Dev
Experimental	30	70	100	86,3	8,009
Control	30	62	95	73,97	8,699

Based on Table 1, the posttest data show the mathematical communication skills of students in the class taught using the Problem Based Learning (PBL) model and the class taught using the scientific approach model. In terms of maximum and minimum scores, the class taught with the Problem Based Learning (PBL) model achieved a maximum score of 100 and a minimum score of 70. In contrast, the class taught with the scientific approach model achieved a maximum score of 95 and a minimum score of 62. This indicates that both the maximum and minimum scores in the class using the Problem Based Learning (PBL) model were higher compared to those in the class taught using the scientific approach model.

In terms of average scores, the class taught with the Problem Based Learning (PBL) model achieved an average score of 86.3, while the class taught with the conventional learning model achieved an average score of 73.97. Thus, the difference in average scores was 12.33. This means that the mathematical communication skills of students in the class taught using the Problem Based Learning (PBL) model were higher than those of students in the class taught using the scientific approach model.

Furthermore, to evaluate the impact of the Problem Based Learning (PBL) model and the scientific approach on improving students' mathematical beliefs, a further analysis was conducted by reviewing the recap of students' mathematical belief data from the posttest results. The analysis results are presented in Table 2 below.

Table 2. Students' Mathematical Beliefs Data

Class	Number of Students	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Dev
Experimental	30	75	98	83	5,539
Control	30	50	88	74,26	9,515

Based on Table 2, the data show the post-test results of students' mathematical beliefs in the class taught using the Problem Based Learning (PBL) model and the class taught using the scientific approach model. In terms of the maximum and minimum scores, the class taught with the PBL model achieved a maximum score of 98 and a minimum score of 75. Meanwhile, the class taught with the scientific approach achieved a maximum score of 88 and a minimum score of 50. This indicates that both the maximum and minimum scores in the PBL class were higher than those in the class taught using the scientific approach.

In terms of the mean scores, the class taught using the PBL model had an average score of 83, while the class taught using the conventional approach had an average score of 74.26, resulting in a difference of 8.74. This means that students' mathematical beliefs in the PBL class were higher than those in the class taught with the scientific approach. From these data, it can be descriptively concluded that the class receiving the PBL treatment obtained higher scores than the class receiving the scientific approach treatment, suggesting that PBL has an effect, although improvements are still needed. To confirm this statement, inferential testing was conducted. The statistical analysis proceeded with inferential tests; however, before conducting the inferential analysis, assumption testing needed to be fulfilled. The assumption tests in this study included the normality test and the homogeneity test of the post-test results for the experimental and control classes. These tests were used as prerequisites for conducting an independent ttest as a parametric test. The normality test used in this study was the Shapiro-Wilk test, as the sample size was fewer than 100 participants.

Table 3. Normality Test

Class	Significance	Description
Experimental	0,121	Normal
Control	0,062	Normal

Based on Table 3, it can be seen that the significance value for the experimental class is 0.121 and for the control class is 0.062, which meets the normality requirement. Both classes

have significance values greater than 0.05, indicating that the data are normally distributed.

The next test is the homogeneity test. The homogeneity test used in this study is Levene's test. The results of the homogeneity test for the experimental and control classes are presented below.

Table 4. Homogeneity Test Levenne

Significance	Description	Statistic
0,535	0,468	homogeneous

Based on Table 4, the significance value is 0.468, where $0.468 > 0.05$, indicating that the posttest results of the experimental and control classes come from a homogeneous population. The requirements for the parametric hypothesis test are met, namely that the data are normally distributed and homogeneous; therefore, the data analysis can proceed using the Hotelling's T^2 test and the Independent t-test. The following are the results of the Hotelling's T^2 test and the Independent Samples t-test using SPSS 25 software.

Table 5. Hotelling T^2 test

Data	F	Significance
Posttest	1,508	0,022

Based on Table 5, it can be seen that the post-treatment data show a Sig. value < 0.05 , indicating that H_0 is rejected. This suggests that there is a difference between the two classes in terms of students' mathematical communication skills and mathematical beliefs. Since H_0 is rejected, a post hoc or follow-up test needs to be conducted to determine which learning approach is superior for each of the tested variables.

Table 6. Independent Sample T-Test

Variable	t	Significance
Mathematical communication skills	5,713	0,000
Mathematical beliefs	4,344	0,000

Data analysis using the Hotelling T^2 test showed a significant difference between the two classes. Furthermore, the independent t-test results also indicated that learning with the PBL model was superior to learning with the scientific approach in terms of students' mathematical communication skills and mathematical beliefs. The findings of this research are supported by other studies. For instance, Silmi Ghaida (2024) concluded that students who learned through a scientific approach combined with the PBL model achieved higher mathematical communication skills compared to students who learned only through the scientific approach (without PBL). Similarly, research by Kurnia Wati and Selvi Loviana (2021) at SMPN 4 Abung Timur found that students

taught using PBL showed significantly higher mathematical communication scores than those taught through the scientific approach. In their study, PBL provided students with greater opportunities to participate actively and express ideas during the learning process.

Similar results were found in research by Rahmalia, Hajidin, and Ansari (2021), which proved that the application of PBL could enhance students' mathematical communication skills as well as their positive dispositions toward mathematics. This study, conducted at SMP Negeri 9 Langsa, showed that students were able to express their mathematical ideas more clearly, both in written and oral form, after participating in problem-based learning. From these findings, it can be concluded that PBL has a significant impact on strengthening students' mathematical communication skills. This is because, in PBL, students are actively involved in the learning process, especially in formulating, interpreting, and presenting mathematical solutions logically and systematically.

In addition to communication skills, students' mathematical beliefs are also an important aspect of learning. Mathematical belief includes students' belief in the value of mathematics in life, perceptions of mathematics teaching, self-confidence in solving problems, and views on the social role of mathematics. Several studies show that the impact of PBL on mathematical beliefs is still varied. For example, research by Yuliana et al. (2017) concluded that although PBL was effective in improving mathematical communication, there was no significant effect on students' mathematical beliefs. Similarly, Luftianingtyas et al. (2015) reported that the increase in students' beliefs was not as great as the improvement in cognitive aspects such as communication or problem solving. This aligns with the findings of Sinaga et al. (2024), which indicated that students experienced increased self-confidence, courage to express ideas, and positive attitudes toward mathematics after engaging in problem-based learning designed with a collaborative and reflective approach.

IV. CONCLUSION

Based on the results obtained, the conclusion of this study is that the Problem-Based Learning (PBL) model has an effect on students' mathematical communication skills and mathematical beliefs. PBL instruction is also superior to instruction using the scientific approach in terms of mathematical communication skills and mathematical beliefs of seventh-grade students in the topic of statistics.

This conclusion is supported by the finding of a significant difference between the experimental class, which was taught using the Problem-Based Learning (PBL) model, and the control class, which was taught using only the scientific approach. The experimental class achieved a higher average score in both mathematical communication skills and mathematical beliefs compared to the control class.

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